

Summer Games Report – Vector Based Team

Individual Pitch Control for Lidar-Assisted Wind Turbine Control

IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games 2025

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Abstract

The Summer Games are an international challenge organized by the IEA Task 52 which aims to advance wind turbine control strategies using lidar-assisted control. Following the decision on focusing on the 30 s sprint challenge, the vector based team tried to optimize the controller for the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine using Individual Pitch Control: this addition to the controller aimed to regulating the wind turbine to react specifically to the wind disturbances coming from wind shear, which create imbalances on the rotor and contribute to the Vertical and Horizontal moments on the non rotating plane. This report showcases the architecture of the newly implemented IPC, added to the already existing Feedback + Feedforward Collective Pitch Controller, and the measures taken to tune the controller to have the best response to the disturbances, following the final goal of optimizing the cost function of the controller.

1 Introduction

The dynamic nature of wind characterized by stochastic changes in speed, direction, and turbulence present a significant challenge for wind turbine control systems. Conventional feedback controllers are inherently reactive; they can only compensate for wind disturbances after the forces have already impacted the turbine structure and manifested in the output data. This delay often leads to increased fatigue, extreme loads, and higher actuator wear.

To address these limitations, Lidar-Assisted Control (LAC) utilizes Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) systems to provide a "preview" of incoming wind disturbances. By measuring wind characteristics at various distances in front of the rotor, the controller can anticipate changes and initiate pitch adjustments before the disturbance reaches the turbine. This "look-ahead" capability allows for a predictive feed forward strategy that significantly reduces turbine loads compared to baseline feedback systems.

Building on the collaborative framework of the 2024 and 2025 Summer Games [1], this report explores the application of LAC within realistic, high-fidelity environments. Utilizing open-source tools and reference models like the IEA 15 MW turbine and the ROSCO controller, this study evaluates how look-ahead cyclic pitch control can mitigate asymmetric loads caused by horizontal and vertical wind shear.

The 2025 Summer Games, in particular, focuses on two different challenges for the controller:

- 30 s sprint, where a Extreme Coherent gust with Direction change strikes the wind turbine, following the Design Load Case (DLC) 1.4, used for simulation of an extreme case as described by the IEC 61400-1 standard for wind turbine design [2]. This challenge requires a special focus on the turbine controller design optimization, to achieve the best performance possible of the turbine when subjected to an extreme load case as the one described above.
- 18 m/s Hurdles, where a turbulent wind field at a high wind speed strikes the turbine. This challenge focuses more on the wind preview optimization from the lidar data, improving the algorithm used by the controller to quantify the Rotor Effective Wind Speed that hits the turbine.

The Vector Based team, for the Summer Games 2025 decided to focus more on the 30 s sprint, looking for a significant improvement of the feedback + feedforward Pitch Controller for the IEA 15 MW turbine.

1.1 Objective

The main objective of the Summer Games is related to the reduction of the so-called cost function for the simulation, described as:

$$J = \frac{\max(\Omega - \Omega_0)}{\Omega_0} + \frac{\max(|M_{yT} - M_{yT0}|)}{M_{yT0}} \quad (1)$$

Where Ω is the rotational speed of the rotor and M_{yT} is the fore-aft tower base bending moment, and Ω_0 and M_{yT0} are the steady-state values of the respective values. The cost function is, therefore, an indication of how the controller counters the effects of the wind striking the rotor by using a feedback + feedforward control system. The latter, as already mentioned above, makes use of the wind preview obtained from the lidar measurements at a certain distance to make the controller react to the wind before it reaches the turbine, significantly reducing the effects on the turbine.

Following the decision to focus on the 30 s sprint challenge, the main goal of the Vector Based team was to optimize the turbine controller to react to an extreme load case such as the one described in the DLC 1.4. In this case, the extreme gust with direction change happens at a wind speed above rated, starting at an initial speed of 12.5 m/s, together with a sudden direction change, requiring the turbine to reduce the effects of these sudden changes in the wind field. To improve the turbine performance the focus of the Vector Based team was placed on the reaction to the high wind shears that rise from the extreme load case. These influence the turbine rotor, creating high imbalances on the vertical and horizontal direction on the rotor plane which are particularly relevant in the case of a turbine with a relatively big size, such as the one used for simulations in this case.

The main objective of the challenge is then to improve the controller, aiming to reduce the imbalance effects of the loads on the rotor implementing an Individual Pitch Controller to the ROSCO controller architecture, as will be explained further in the next section, with main goal of minimizing the cost function.

The report will be structured starting with a general overview of the controller architecture, which will be followed by a description of the initial validation of the lidar estimation for under simplified condition and, at the very end, by a showcase of the results for the main challenge and the future improvements that can be implemented into the controller

2 System Description

Following the introduction to the concepts behind the Summer Games and the specific objectives of the Vector Based Group, this section will explain how the wind turbine simulations are conducted and the final architecture of the controller and its characteristics in line with the focus the Vector Based Group has put on the implementation of the **Individual Pitch Controller**.

The optimization is performed on the IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine, using the parameters provided in the OpenFAST files, software used to simulate the turbine performances. The task is performed via a Matlab/Simulink based code, used to reproduce the effects of the wind on the wind turbine.

The Simulation is run by using a Simulink model, which reproduces the open-source controller ROSCO [3]. As shown in Figure 1, the base Simulink model is mainly composed of a Collective Pitch Controller (CPC) divided into a feedback baseline controller and a feedback controller based on LAC connected to the OpenFAST turbine simulation tool for the IEA 15 MW turbine.

As already mentioned, the Vector Based Team focused on the implementation of an additional Individual Pitch Controller (IPC) complementary to the already existing Collective Pitch Controller in the ROSCO based Simulink model.

This additional controller consists also of a Feedback part, based on a Linear Time Invariant model, and a Feedforward part, which again makes use of the Lidar Preview Data to optimize the reaction of the controller.

Figure 1: Simulink model for the ROSCO controller, including the newly implemented Individual Pitch Controller.

2.1 Feedback Individual Pitch Controller

The Feedback part, presented in Figure 2 is based on the manipulation of the **out of plane root blade bending moments**, the bending moments relative to the blades in the rotating plane. This aims to reduce the rotor imbalances, brought by the vertical and horizontal shears of the wind field, which affects the value of the vertical and horizontal in plane moments (respectively the so-called “Yaw Moment” and “Tilt Moment”). This is particularly relevant when simulating an extreme load case such as DLC 1.4 including a sudden direction change which can greatly affect the rotor loading.

The three out of plane blade bending moments of the blades are transformed into the Vertical and Horizontal bending moments in the fixed frame of the rotor plane M_V and M_H using a Multiblade Coordinate Transformation (or *Coleman Transformation*) [4]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} M_H(t) \\ M_V(t) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2}{3} \cos(\psi(t)) & \frac{2}{3} \cos(\psi(t) + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \frac{2}{3} \cos(\psi(t) + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \\ \frac{2}{3} \sin(\psi(t)) & \frac{2}{3} \sin(\psi(t) + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \frac{2}{3} \sin(\psi(t) + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} M_1(t) \\ M_2(t) \\ M_3(t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

Where $\psi(t)$ is the azimuth angle for the blade subject to M_1 .

This transformation is necessary since M_V and M_H are used as control inputs for the two PI controllers used to minimize the effects of the moments on the vertical and horizontal axis. The outputs of the controllers are the control signals for the pitch angles in the vertical and horizontal non-rotating frame, used to obtain the necessary additional pitch angles of the single blades via the inverse Multiblade Coordinate transformation (or *Inverse Coleman*) [4]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \theta_1 \\ \theta_2 \\ \theta_3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\psi(t)) & \sin(\psi(t)) \\ \cos(\psi(t) + \frac{2}{3}\pi) & \sin(\psi(t) + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ \cos(\psi(t) + \frac{4}{3}\pi) & \sin(\psi(t) + \frac{4}{3}\pi) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \theta_H \\ \theta_V \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Feedforward Individual Pitch Controller

To additionally compensate the effects of the ECD for the 30 s Sprint challenge, the controller uses the LAC approach to implement an additional feedforward part to the Individual Pitch controller to improve the reaction to the vertical and horizontal rotor imbalance effects.

This part of the controller is divided into two main functions: the estimation of the wind shears as control inputs and the actual feedforward controller, as will be explained in the next section.

Figure 2: Individual Pitch Controller.

2.2.1 Wind Shears Estimation

To implement Lidar Assisted Control to the IPC the Lidar data, namely the line-of-sight speed v_{los} , is used to calculate the disturbances that are of main interest to the Individual Pitch Control: the horizontal and vertical wind shears δ_H and δ_V .

These values are calculated starting from the inhomogenous dynamic wind model presented in [5]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} u_{i,w} \\ v_{i,w} \\ w_{i,w} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v_0(t) + \delta_H(t)y_{i,w} + \delta_V(t)z_{i,w} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Which models the wind as inhomogeneous, simply composed of the horizontal component. For the lidar estimation, the v_0 , which represents the estimation of the Rotor Effective Wind Speed (REWS), and the shears are estimated by the lidar from v_{los} of the different measurement points, using the following equation [5]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} v_{los,1} \\ \vdots \\ v_{los,n_P} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_{n,1,I} & x_{n,1,I}y_{1,I} & x_{n,1,I}z_{1,I} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ x_{n,n_P,I} & x_{n,n_P,I}y_{n_P,I} & x_{n,n_P,I}z_{n_P,I} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v_{0,L} \\ \delta_{H,L} \\ \delta_{V,L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Where $x_{n,i,I}$ is the normalized axial position of the lidar measurement points and $y_{i,I}$ and $z_{i,I}$ are the horizontal and vertical positions of the lidar measurement points on the plane normal to the axial direction, $v_{los,i}$ is the line of sight speed of i -th lidar measurement point and $\delta_{V,L}$ and $\delta_{H,L}$ are the lidar estimates of the vertical and horizontal wind shears. v_{los,n_P} indicates the number of beam points.

2.2.2 Feedforward/look ahead controller

The lidar estimations for the vertical and horizontal wind shears are essential to regulate the imbalances over the rotor, by regulating the pitch angles of the blades via a feedforward Individual Pitch Controller (FF-IPC).

The Vector Based team designed the FF-IPC following the structure presented in [6]. Here the asynchronous part of the feedforward pitch controller (namely the one used to regulate the vertical and horizontal shear effects) uses a set of gains that compensate the influence of the horizontal and vertical disturbances of the wind, obtaining the necessary input signals to the double PI feedback pitch controller as additional values of the pitch angles in the horizontal and vertical non-rotating axes:

$$u_{ss,HV} = \begin{bmatrix} g_H & 0 \\ 0 & g_V \end{bmatrix} d_{ss,HV} \quad (6)$$

$$\theta_{H,FF} = g_H \delta_H \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_{V,FF} = g_V \delta_V \quad (8)$$

Where $u_{ss,HV}$ is the steady-state vector of feedforward individual pitch demands in the non-rotating frame, whose components $\theta_{H,FF}$ and $\theta_{V,FF}$ are the horizontal and vertical pitch contributions, respectively. $d_{ss,HV}$ is the corresponding steady-state disturbance vector containing the lidar-estimated horizontal and vertical wind shears $\delta_{H,L}$ and $\delta_{V,L}$. The diagonal gain matrix maps each shear component to its associated pitch demand through the feedforward gains g_H and g_V , which are tuned independently for the horizontal and vertical channels.

3 Methodology

Summer games 2025 utilizes IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine for simulations and modified version of OpenFAST v3.0 for lidar simulations. As mentioned, extreme coherent gust with direction change is used to evaluate controllers. To use the FF-IPC that is proposed in this report, first it is necessary to confirm that shear can be estimated without an error for both lidar setups, a four-beam pulsed and circular continuous-wave.

When shear can be estimated successfully, gains can be tuned. In this report, the aim is to measure the vertical shear, thus determining the vertical gain only, with the goal of simplifying the simulations. Since the team has been only focusing on vertical shear, as an objective of IPC as well, the main focus was to minimize the vertical moments derived from the flap wise moments at the blade root.

For both shear estimation and gain tuning, a steady wind speed is at hub height of 12.5 m/s is used to generate four different wind fields with different vertical shear, assuming no horizontal shear. As it is not possible to use steady wind conditions in InflowFile for this OpenFAST version, Bladed-style wind fields is generated to simulate the steady wind conditions. As mentioned before this simplified simulation setup is used to determine the validity of the controller setup by starting from a more basic wind field, before validating it for the actual main task of the challenge: the DLC 1.4.

3.1 Estimation of the wind shear from the lidar measurement

To evaluate the accuracy of the wind shear estimation the data needs to be independent from the model and its disturbances. For this reason many different simplifications are introduced for this initial simulation case:

- Lidar volume averaging is disabled
- Tower and Blade degrees of freedom are disabled
- Linear interpolation is used by the lidar simulator to reconstruct the wind field
- Tilt and Cone angles are set to zero

Under these conditions the vertical shear can be estimated from line-of-sight velocity measurements. Vertical shear is estimated by using Equation (5), saving each velocity measurement and corresponding beam coordinates into a matrix, then using least-squares fit to get the shears.

Table ?? presents the vertical wind shear estimation obtained from both lidar types alongside the corresponding wind field values. It can be observed that circular continuous wave can measure the vertical shear without an error but for the 4 beams pulsed, it measure with very low errors. This error is small enough to be negligible and might be caused of the less measurement points for least-squares fit.

Reference δ_V [(m/s)/m]	4-Beam Pulsed $\hat{\delta}_{V,L}$ [(m/s)/m]	Circular CW $\hat{\delta}_{V,L}$ [(m/s)/m]
0.01200	0.01199	0.01200
0.01600	0.01599	0.01600
0.02000	0.01999	0.02000
0.02400	0.02399	0.02400

Table 1: Comparison of vertical wind shear estimates from the two lidar configurations against the reference wind field values.

3.2 Look Ahead Controller Tuning

In order to cancel the effect of the vertical shears, the look ahead controller described in Section 2 is used. As mentioned above, in this report only the vertical moment is analyzed, while assuming the absence of any horizontal shear. To find the proper gain for this simulation, all degrees of freedom are disabled except for the generator, together with pitch actuator, responsible for furtherly delaying the signal. Additionally, only the feedforward section from Section 2.2.2 is used for IPC, with the vertical pitch signal being fed alone into the inverse Coleman transformation to produce the individual blade pitch angle offsets.

As one of the aims of the IPC is to cancel vertical moment, with the given settings, different gains are run with steady wind. It is seen in Figure 3 when gain of 1.4 is applied, it minimizes the amplitude of RootMyb1 and vertical moment is almost zero.

Figure 4 shows the comparison of pitch angle, blade-root out-of-plane bending moment and vertical moment between the case where the gain is zero, removing the effects of the IPC, and where the optimal gain of 1.4 is used. Although a phase mismatch between pitch angle and blade-root out-of-plane bending moment can be observed when the gain is applied, the results demonstrate that vertical moment is successfully reduced to zero by the IPC.

Figure 3: Comparison between the amplitude of the Out of Plane Moment and the Vertical Moment

Figure 4: Steady wind simulation for 4 different constant wind shear values without azimuth offset

The phase offset is most likely caused by peak of the loads not matching the rotor azimuth position signal that goes to the Coleman transformation in the IPC. Thus, an azimuth offset is introduced before the transformation to align both signals. Figure 5 shows the results of the simulation when the azimuth offset is implemented, making it possible to compare them to the ones observed in the previous case in Figure 4. Although the match of the phases of the signals is improved, the out-of-plane bending moments at the blade root do not yet match the expected cyclic behavior.

Figure 5: Steady wind simulation for 4 different constant wind shear values with azimuth offset

4 Results

In conclusion to this report, the final results of the simulation of the DLC 1.4 will be showcased in this chapter. Said results will be mainly divided between the two types of Lidar configuration:

- 4-beam pulsed lidar type
- circular continuous wave lidar type

The plots that will be showcased in Figure 6 and Figure 7 reflecting the goal of optimizing the cost function shown in Equation (1). The main results from the DLC 1.4 simulation will be, therefore:

- *the Wind Speed* obtained from the definition in DLC 1.4 and its lidar estimate **in m/s**
- *the pitch angle* **in degrees**
- *the rotor speed* **in rpm**
- *the tower base moment* **in kNm**

Additionally, the results for two of the most important parameters related to the IPC are showcased for the ECD simulation: the vertical shear and the vertical moment time series.

4.1 4 Beam Pulsed Wave results

Figure 6: Main results for the 4 Beam Pulsed wave Lidar configuration. *Left:* vertical shear and moment time series. *Right:* main results for the simulation

4.2 Circular Continuous Wave results

Figure 7: Main results for the Circular Continuous Wave Lidar configuration. *Left:* vertical shear and moment time series. *Right:* main results for the simulation

4.3 Comment on the results

Firstly, in the cases of both lidar types, the proposed controller is able to reduce the cost:

- For the 4BeamPulsed lidar, cost is reduced from **0.7228** to **0.7104**
- For the circular continuous wave cost is reduced from **1.2172** to **0.8053**.

In both cases when vertical moment is inspected, the controller is able to maintain close to zero. However, once the gust hits the turbine, controller is unable to keep the vertical moment caused by the disruptions. But as the gust settles, it goes back to near zero again. This behavior, when combined with vertical shear not being constant throughout the simulation, suggests that controller is not able to follow the varying vertical shear disturbances.

This, as will be explained in the next section, shows that there is still room for improvement to the setup of the controller.

5 Conclusion and Future Work

This report presented the design and evaluation of combined feedback and feedforward individual pitch controller as a part of the Summer Games 2025. The controller is tested with IEA 15 MW reference wind turbine and extreme coherent gust with direction change scenario. Feedback IPC is implemented with Coleman transformation-based PI controller. Feedforward IPC is coupled with feedback IPC, measuring the vertical wind shears in order to calculate a vertical pitch signal which is optimized via gain tuning to eliminate the vertical moments. Cost results of the 30 s sprint simulation are slightly reduced, approximately 3% for 4BeamPulsed and 34% for CircularCW. As the controller is unable to keep the vertical moments close to zero during the gust, further improvements could reduce the cost function even further. Additionally, it is seen that when shear is not constant, controller is unable to entirely fulfill its goals.

There are several changes that could improve the performance of the controller in future work.

1. To employ feedforward horizontal gain to the IPC controller, where it is possible to reduce loads for direction change.
2. Add a low-pass filter can be applied to shear estimations. Shear signal is not at high frequency, but it could be an improvement for realistic wind simulations.
3. As mentioned, controller is ineffective to overcome the disruptions when there is a change in vertical shear, it may be possible to utilize a look-up table for shear-gain, where it needs to be investigated together with azimuth offset.
4. The Bladed-style steady wind field that is generated is not the ideal steady wind, as it can be seen in figure 4 and 5 vertical moment is oscillating, in ideal wind it should have stayed constant. Other methods of creating bladed-style steady wind field could be inspected, or steady or uniform wind type in InflowFile for the OpenFAST could be used before start investigations with lidar simulator, as current version that is used in Summer Games 2025 do not support these wind types.

Nonetheless, although not perfect, the performances of the controller in terms of cost function are improved. This shows how the implementation of the IPC can be a good improvement to the control strategy for this simulation set up: this type of controller can perform particularly well when dealing with a relatively big wind turbine, such as the one in this case, and with a generally more complex extreme load case as DLC 1.4.

The ECD, in particular, can be a relevant testing field especially in regard with the mitigation of the effects of the direction change, which can be performed by an optimized IPC.

References

- [1] D. Schlipf, F. Guo, M. van den Broek and S. Weich "IEA Wind Task 52 LAC Summer Games 2025", 2025
- [2] "Wind turbines-Part 1: Design requirements," 2005. [Online]. Available: www.barghnews.com
- [3] N. J. Abbas, D. S. Zalkind, L. Pao, and A. Wright, "A reference open-source controller for fixed and floating offshore wind turbines," *Wind Energy Science*, vol. 7, no. 1, pp. 53–73, Jan. 2022, doi: 10.5194/wes-7-53-2022.
- [4] Q. Lu, R. Bowyer, and B. L. Jones, "Analysis and design of Coleman transform-based individual pitch controllers for wind-turbine load reduction," *Wind Energy*, vol. 18, no. 8, pp. 1451–1468, Aug. 2015, doi: 10.1002/we.1769.
- [5] D.Schlipf "Lidar Assisted Control Concepts for Wind Turbines", 2015
- [6] D. Schlipf, S. Schuler, P. Grau, F. Allgöwer, and M. K. " Uhn, "Look-Ahead Cyclic Pitch Control Using LIDAR," 2010.